

DEEPENING OF DEMOCRACY IN INDIA**Dr. Kale Sanjay Ankush***Associate Professor**K.V.N.Naik Arts, Commerce and Science College Nashik***Abstract:**

India is the largest and best democracy in the world, which gives its citizen the right to vote, democracy is deeply rooted in India irrespective of their caste, color, creed, religion and gender. There is a need to eliminate gender discrimination, illiteracy, castes and poverty to ensure democracy in India. Social movement are driving India towards deepening of democracy, women play an important role in it. There are procedures and rules which are strengthening the parliament's oversight on government. It leads to sustained and equitable development. Focus should be on effective democracy. Subordinate groups and local government should have ample opportunities to engage meaningfully with the state for deepening democracy.

Deepening of Democracy in India

India is the largest successful democracy among democratic countries, which gives its citizens the right to vote. India became a democratic nation by the year of 1947 after independence irrespective of their religion, creed, caste, colour and gender, democracy is deeply rooted in India. Democratic, republic, socialist, secular and sovereign is the five democratic principles. Democracy gives us a form of government in which people are governed by their own elected representatives. Democracy gives fundamental rights to its voters and individuals. Indian democracy provides the right to vote as well as ensures economic and social equality. Indian democratic system received admiration in the world, but there are many sectors which demands progress, but then it can be arranged in a real recognition. There is also need to eliminate gender discrimination, illiteracy, castism and poverty to ensure democracy in India.

Success of national democracy depends upon the success of democracy at the grass root level. Over 65% of India's population is living in the rural area. India introduced local government system in 1950 called panchayat raj which is constitutionally encouraged. Government of India are both levels such as center level and state level. There is also important system of local government which is called the panchayat raj system. The formation and efforts of four important committees taken to form a system of local self-government in India from the year 1957-1986.

1) Balwant Rai Mehta Committee-1957

2) Ashok Mehta Committee-1977-78

3) U.G.V.K.Rao Committee 1985

4) L.M.Singhvi Committee 1986

The 64th constitutional amendment bill was introduced in Lok Sabha in 1989 which was opposed by Rajya Sabha. It was the Narasimha Rao government who made a reality of the panchayat raj by the 73rd and 74th constitutional amendment acts in 1992. The 73rd constitutional amendment act provides a

gram Sabha ,which is a village assembly consisting of all the registered voters in the area of panchayat raj system . In the local government bodies –

- Direct elections are taken for representation of all seats of local bodies by citizen.
- Seats are reserved for SC and ST candidates according to their population.
- Reservation of one –third seats for women

Performance of panchayat raj is very important for enhancing livelihood, poverty alleviation and more importantly attaining distributive justice. Local government deals with local affairs, administered by authorities subordinate to the state government. It is also a multi-function organization perceiving a variety of political, social, economic objectives either through a direct provision or through the sponsorship or direct funding. The importance of local government lies in sustaining the democracy. If democracy should function properly as many citizens should be inspired and get opportunities to take interest in its activities and problems. People have to work with great presurance and patience in a democracy. If we see back we may find the progress achieved under a democratic system is very firm. Local government has produced many leaders of national importance as Motilal Nehru, Jawaharlal Nehru, Pherozshah Mehta, Subhash Chandra Bose, Vallabhai Patel, Lala Lajpat Rai, etc. in our country, who are shining examples of healthy local politics. These examples justify the best school of democracy and promises for its great victory of the local government.

Each individual is participating in the election, they are so glad to choose a leader of their choice .even today many 19 year old girls have become a sarpanch in the village .these persons are literate as well as have the knowledge of the technologies,politics, developments, abilities of the world. Even people or citizens choose the leader according to their will ,no one will know who will win the election, it not only happens in local level but also state and national level also e.g. elections of 2014 .no other system involves the common people in administration as much as in the democratic system. In democracy the people organizes their own phenomenon ,which is more understandable ,simple ,direct ,straightforward and significant .The supervision of people to their representatives is constant which brings the government and the people close together with one another . According to Lord Bryce ‘the best assurance for the successes of democracy is the practice of local self-government, it is said that involving people at the lowest stratum of society or at the grass-root level with the administration may be said that it is the modern version of direct democracy’. In democratic system, transfer of power is very essential from higher to lower levels ,which brings a fulfilled participation of the sovereignty thoroughly .Local self-government solves the problems at the grass -root level of the rural people which strengthens democracy.

Local self-government encourages local leadership .The real progress and the social –economic conditions of people can occur only through the intentional participation in the developmental programmed and plans .local people should be inspired for solving their problems of their own .framework of centralized state also affect the deepening of democracy in India .The Indian constitutional framers aimed at a federal structure which would be effective in nature by respecting diversity and heterogeneity of the Indian society . Both parliamentary and presidential federal system

has incorporated by the independent of India; however society is very powerful and energetic in which changestaken place within the social context which lead to changes in the text of the constitution.

There are seven national parties in India .these are -

- 1) INC- Indian national congress
- 2) BJP-Bhartiya Janta Party
- 3)CPI-Communist Party of India
- 4)NCP-Nationalist Congress Party
- 5)CPI-MCPI Marxist
- 6)BSP-Bahujan Samaj Party
- 7)TMC-All India Trinamool Congress

India has national as well as regional parties who fight election for vidhan sabha and vidhan parishad [state legislatures). Encouragement of the government to the people for voting is constant, which helps for choosing the best leader for working good government .even Indian democratic system give the people right to vote as well as ensure equal opportunities for living their lives.

In 2012, we saw a positive step for Indian democracy. Before 2012, Indian voters are voting to the identity based parties ,which do not fulfilled the needs of society and do not pay attention on the progress of the nation in a real sense.Choosing Parties finding emphatically rejected they at the cause formed in 1960 a rigid reaction against the powerful congress party. Appealing to voter’s language, caste, itnicity and religion, this group built political support, this type of action had been largely successful in the past. As in the 21st century, Indian voters vote them who are really trying to fulfilled needs of societies very truly, but not to those who is loyal to particular caste or religion. In 2010, reelection of chief minister Nitish Kumar in eastern state of Bihar is the most emblematic of this step. Many identity based parties are remerging on the basis of performance. Support from Muslim base, Samajwadi Party of Uttar Pradesh won with increased support but poor performance of Mayavati had lost because her Dalit base fed up. India still struggles with caste based was fed up. India still struggle with caste based violence, discrimination and religious extremism. Indian democracy is strengthening by regional politics. Indian people are demanding more from their government and parties which are responding them with stronger platforms, more competitive elections and better governance. Even Narendra Modi looked hopefully to national elections in 2014.

Democracy has taken its root as well as it has spread wide and deep over the last five decades in India. our democracy seek to look after the benefits of its people .democracy has detailed and long constitution with having good features .it has comprehensive understanding of the rights of the citizens and genuine procedure for the functioning of the government . Basic structure of the constitution is fundamental rights and directive principles .protection to its people and development of o the country is the main agenda of the Indian democracy. The Indian Constitution of part iii gives thepeople fundamental rights. These rights are the basic rights of the citizens which are shared by all .the constitution classifies seven fundamental rights which are as follows;

- Right to equality
- Right to freedom

- Right against exploitation
- Right to freedom of religion
- Cultural and educational right
- Right to property
- Right to constitutional remedies

Right to equality plays crucial role in society .there is no discrimination to religion, race, caste, sex or place of birth .everyone should be equal before the law, even there is equal opportunity to all the citizens in matter of public employment .there is special provision of the reservation of posts for citizens who belong to scheduled castes, scheduled tribes and other backward classes. Abolition of untouchability is also seen in India after independence. Practicing of untouchability is made a punishable offence under a law. This provision is an attempt to uplift the social status of millions of Indians who had been kept at a distance of either the nature of profession or their caste. According to a news report of PTI [press trust of India), on January 3, 2014, four tea shop seller were arrested in Karnataka by the police for practicing untouchability while selling tea. They were used different cups for serving according to their caste status. However, it can be said that things are changing slowly. New generation is changing their mindset.

Right against exploitation is very important in India, in its traffic in human being and beggar are prohibited and punishable in accordance with law. Trafficking for commercial sexual exploitation, under the immoral, trafficking prevention act (ITPA) is penalized punishment for this crime is ranges from seven years to life imprisonment. In India, the bonded labor abolition act, the child labor act and the juvenile justice act prohibit the bonded and force labor. Better education and other basic facilities should be provided to the native places by which parents will not opt this ways for their kids. Right to freedom is the most admiring desire of every living being. The constitution of India provides six rights to freedom the main purpose of providing freedom is to build and maintain an environment for proper functioning of democracy. Every one experience this freedom plays most importance role in India as there is multilingual and multicasts, though each and every person is living anywhere in a very peaceful way.

- 1) They have freedom of speech and expression.
- 2) Freedom to move freely throughout the territory of India.
- 3) Freedom to reside and settle in any part of India.
- 4) Freedom to assemble peacefully and without arms.
- 5) Freedom to form associations and unions.
- 6) Freedom to practice any professions or to carry on any occupation, trade or business.

In India we see many cities such as Delhi, Gujarat, Mumbai, Nagpur, Pune, Nashik and many more, people from another state places, cities are living together though they have different languages, caste and religion. They have unity and they are not feeling fear to go another state and cities.

As India is multi-religious country, where Hindus, Muslim, Christians, Sikhs and many other communities living together. The constitution of India declares “India as a secular state” which means Indian state has no religion of its own but it allows all the citizen to have faith in any religion, can

worship the way they like. This freedom do not only allows our country people but also foreigners, in the same way they should not interfere with the religious beliefs and ways of worship of others. India is the largest democracy in the world who have diversity of Culture, language, scripts and religion, as we know that Democracy is rule of the majority but minorities also have equal importance for successful of working, there for protection of culture, religion and language of the minorities become important. In this way minorities may not feel neglected by the majority of rule. Even or minorities whether they are based on religion or language can establish and administer educational institution of their choice. Minority does not mean minority at the national level, it can be at the state level also, e.g. in Punjab Sikhs are majority community but in the same time they are in Delhi, Haryana, Rajasthan, Maharashtra and other states as a minor community.

Right to education is added by introducing new article 21A in the chapter on fundamental rights in 2002 by the 86th constitutional amendment. By fundamental right, all children who are in the age group of six to fourteen years get free and compulsory education. Here free means that child shall not pay any kind of fee of expenses which may prevent her him from completing elementary education. The state is seen as the chief provider education today. From 1st April 2010, it becomes most important upon a state to provide quality education to the children. There must be 25% reservation in private as well as minorities schools for poor children but the implementation of RTE at act faces massive man power, financial problem and logistics. There is shortage of qualified teacher across government school especially in rural area.

The constitution of India was framed on 26th of January 1950 which is the world's longest written constitution from that time democracy ushered in India in the preamble of the of the constitution, the pledge to make India democratic ,republic and ascertain equality ,liberty and justice to all its citizen s. there are three type of justice ,which are political ,social and economic .it is considered to be the primary goal of a welfare of a state schemes are also important for the satisfaction of the citizens of our country. The ministries of the government of India have come up with many useful schemes can both central and state or joint collaboration of centre as well as the state.

Many schemes such as

- Atal pension yojana
- Digital India programme
- Pradhan mantri gram in awas yojna
- Intetrated Rural Development Program
- Namami Gange Programme
- Sampoorna Grameen Rojgar Yojna

Such schemes are essential for the success of democracy, wherepeople do their work happily not for themselves but also for the development of country. Citizens not only literate but also illiterate who are in their old age taking benefits of schemes in urban as well as in rural area.

Protection against an injustice, people has come together in large number for several times to the worldwide .Indians were also touched by the wave of the movements. swadeshi movement and

satyagrah were used by mahatma Gandhi. In the past, India saw some of the most powerful movements which led turning points for change in society. Movements help for making decisions collectively and brought the nation together. Indian people prefer peaceful ways are the unique quality of the

movement. many movements such as

- 1) Save silent valley movement -1973
- 2) Chipko movement -1973
- 3) Jungal bachao andolan -1980
- 4) Narmada bachao andolan -1985
- 5) Jan lokpal bill-Anti corruption movement by Anna Hazare 2011
- 6) Nirbhaya movements-2012

Thousands of people or citizen of the country came out on streets to protest their rights, for justice, for safety, for saving nature. Taking into consideration, the government of the centre as well as states announced several steps and even made a law. People of our country are aware as they are literate. Movements are very useful for the success of democracy where people, government and opposition parties are active facing to each other.

Women as a gender category have encountered systematic disabilities woven around socio political structures of dominance and deprivation in the past. However women are moderately proving to be an indispensable part of every sphere of life ranging from family to family to the larger domains of economy and politics, women play an important role in Indian democracy today's chief ministers "Amma" and "Didi" are very influencing in a state as well as national level politics. We cannot forget Vasundara Raje. We have very powerful cabinet minister like Smt Sushma Swaraj. We have leaders like Sonia Gandhi, Preeti Gandhi of national parties irrespective of gender, Indian political system gives same role and powers to the men and women. India had Ms Indira Gandhi as the prime minister of the country for 15 years. Many states had and have many woman chief ministers. External affairs minister Shrimati Sushma Swaraj, Inc President Ms Sonia Gandhi, Lok Sabha speaker Sumitra Mahajan, late Tamil Nadu CM Jayalalita, Vasundara Raje, Sindhia present Rajasthan CM, all these women played decisive and prominent rule in the politics of modern India. In reality, checking the grass roots of Indian political systems, we can realize the role of women is just restricted to vote bank. Government has done various measures towards this. The 73rd constitutional amendment act (statutory provisions) for panchayat raj as third levels of administrations in villages and the 74th constitutional amendment act (statutory provisions for local administrative bodies as third level of administration in urban areas such as towns and cities) provide for 50% reservation in both the bodies. These amendments give rise to the participation of women in the electoral process but most of the times the elected women representations are puppets of their husbands or other main members of the family. Such pictures show gloomy of the democratic system. But we get other good input due to the increased participation of the women. In UP, a 112 year old lady became a gram pradhan last year. Sarpanch of the village Sodha, 60 kilometers from Jaipur, Rajasthan Ms Chavirajvat, is well known for her progressive works in a village especially for women. We have seen many old women become sarpanch in villages. As a result, India has taken a great lead in the role of women in politics. But still there are many areas and

society which the government need to transform and must work on it. The number of women members of parliament and member of legislative assemblies are still very slow.

In the 21st century such as female infanticide, woman security, low sex ratio, woman illiteracy, higher maternity death rates are in front of the nation. It depends on the women as well the people of India to work for women's upliftment and taking active participation in Indian politics.

India is the largest democracy in the world. It has worked successfully for more than 60 years but in modern India it has to face many problems as well as challenges that should be solved in order to ensure true democracy. These challenges include corruption, over population, improper sanitation, poverty and tremendous gap between the rich and poor. Illiteracy, communal violence, right to education, religion, terrorism, caste related violence, law and order, good governance, relationship between neighboring countries, protection of human rights, women and children's right and right to development, implementation of schemes, environmental protections, media, frequent strikes and dharna's, non-cooperation movement, etc. For reforming democracy, Indian government should develop new political, legal and social proposals. Law is significant for political reformation, which will always help to stop false practices .For getting favorable outcome of these challenges, both government as well as opposition should act with realistic parliamentary spirit.

References

- 1) Bhattacharyya ,Harihar ,Making Local Democracy Work in India :Social Capital, Politics and Governance in West Bengal, Vedams ebooks Publishing LTD, New Delhi ,2002 page no .3
- 2) Ganguly ,Domond ,Plattner ,The State of India's Democracy ,Johns Hopkins University Pres, Baltimore, 2007
- 3) Hauck ,Christoph , ,What Role do Elections Play in Social Change in India,2010www.academia.edu ,
- 4) Kishwar ,M.p.,Deepening Democracy :Challenges of Governance and Globalization in India,,Oxford University Press,2006,page no. 162
- 5) Naik ,Sushant Kumar, V. Anil Kumar , Federation and the Formation of States in India,The Institute for Social and Economic Change Bangalore,2016.page no. 5
- 6) Rai Udai Raj ,Fundamental Rights and Their Enforcement,PHI learning pvt LTD ,2011,page no. 3
- 7) Rajmangal Dharmendra,Fundamental Rights of every Indian Citizen,Rajmangal publisher Aligrah (UP)India,2018, page no. 3-18
- 8) Sadanandan ,Anoop ,Why Democracy Deepens ,Cambridge University Press, 2017.
- 9) Sharma shailja , Democracy in india ,www.indiacelebrating.com
- 10) TBI Team ,<http://www.betterindia.com-2015>
- 11) Tripathi Suresh Mani,Fundamental Rights and Directive Principles in India,Anchor Academic Publishing ,2016 page no. 67,113.
- 12) Varma Unikrishna, evolution of local self government (panchayati raj system)in India.<https://www.clearias.com>.